
DISASTER MANAGEMENT AND SECURITY PRECAUTIONS IN SANGLI NAGER VACHNALYA SANGLI

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Abstract:

This study discusses the present status of the disaster management in Sangli (Jilha) Nager Vachnalya, public library of Sangli city. It also identify the hazardous elements that can cause a disaster in Sangli Nager Vachnalya and availability of preventative measures in the library. Survey method was used in this study questionnaire and interview techniques were used for data collection and purposive sampling method was used. Data was presented in the tabular form. The study revealed that Sangli Nager Vachnalya library have a disaster management plan, most of the digital and biological disaster preventive measures are available but the building is not earthquake resistant and library have high possibility of disaster due to water and poor drainage system. Based on the findings, recommendations were made on the importance of disaster management and safety preventive measures.

Keywords: *Disaster, Disaster Management, Digital Disaster, Preventive Measures, Public Library.*

Introduction:

A disaster is, “Any incident which threatens human safety and/or damages, or threatens to damage [or destroy], a library’s buildings, collections, contents, facilities or services” (Matthews and Eden, 1996).

Disasters occurring in libraries are mainly of two types, natural and man-made. Disasters caused by nature which consists of floods, earthquakes, and tornadoes. Disasters caused by humans consist of civil unrest, arson, and vandalism. Disasters of all types and scales have the potential to damage or destroy physical and digital library collections. The specific quality of library disasters are unexpected and inevitable. People generally think that disasters are sudden

events that happen within seconds or minutes. But some disasters happen slowly and we are not aware of it like leaking roofs, dripping pipes, building deficiencies, combustible substance placed in the library or near the library, fungus, termites and insects. The gradual loss of the library due to these calamities is not noticeable.

Disaster management planning is becoming an essential component for libraries to provide the best protection for their collections. Disasters can strike at any time in small or large scale but if an organization is prepared with the right plan, losses can be minimized or avoided. Many libraries were affected by the calamities and were unable to provide services to their users. Therefore, it is

imperative to establish adequate measures to reduce the incidence of potential disasters. Preventive measures help to reduce the extent of damage and help in the recovery process.

Sangli city, was affected by floods in 2019. The lack of preventive planning it has seen that large amount of important information is destroyed. The purpose of the study was to investigate disaster preparedness in public libraries using case study of Nager Vachnalya Sangli.

Need of the Study:

Public libraries play an important role in lifelong learning. They are social institutions developed in society to provide free access to information. They provide information according to educational demands, entertainment and needs of the society. Public libraries are a local centre of information. They provide all kinds of knowledge and information to all groups in the community. The resources available in public libraries are valuable. Thus it is one of the most important responsibilities of library professionals to preserve these resources for future use. To prevent these libraries from any kind of disaster, there should be the provision of adequate disaster preventive equipment and facilities.

Due to the lack of preventive planning, valuable resources of Sangli Nager Vachnalya was destroyed in 2019 flood. Therefore, the researcher wants to find out the existing status and find out the concrete solution on it. The intention of this case study is also to create awareness among the library staff about disaster management and to prevent future losses due to such disasters.

Statement of the Study:

Disaster Management and Security Precautions in Sangli Nager Vachnalya, Sangli

Objective of the Study:

1. To identify the hazardous elements that can cause a disaster in Sangli Nager Vachnalya.
2. To find out the availability of preventive measures in Sangli Nager Vachnalya.

Scope of the Study:

1. The present study covers the aspects of disaster management.
2. The present study covers the aspects of preventive measures of disaster management such as fire preventive disaster management, digital disaster preventive management, water preventive disaster management etc.

Delimitations of the Study:

1. The present study is limited to disaster management and preventive measures.
2. The present study is limited to only public libraries.
3. The present study is limited to Sangli Nager Vachnalya only.

Research Methodology:

Being a case study survey method was used. A well structured questionnaire and interview techniques were used to collect data from the librarian. The data is presented in tabular form.

Sampling:

Sangli (Jilha) Nager Vachnalya, Public Library of Sangli city was selected for the study by using purposive sampling method.

Review of Related Research:

For this study researcher collected data on disaster management, hazardous elements and library security preventive measures. **Lorenzen (1996)** reported different forms of collection distortions like highlighting text, tearing pages and explain in the margins of the books. So it is not viable for users. **Balon and Gardner (2006)** noted that a disaster plan must be implemented for the building and all its contents, people, collections, records and equipment. It's desirable to create this plan by a team rather than by an individual. **Eden and Mathews (1997)** identified the following as some of the problems of disaster management: inadequate exits in the library, non-functioning firefighting equipment and faulty lifts. Research shows that many organizations with disaster plans rarely update and test them. Staffs are not trained. **Mathews (2005)** stated that, as a result of resource constraints, It is wise to engage in cooperative initiatives and networks so that libraries can use resources together to help prevent or mitigate the effects of a disaster. **McEntire and Myers (2004)** noted that one of the most common causes of failure in disaster management is lack of employee awareness. The issue of awareness is, at its most basic level, a managerial responsibility. Which is committed to a continuous disaster management process and supported by trained staff because prevention is important, staff must be prepared to report on maintenance issues that may arise apart from keeping abreast of changes in procedures or changes in contact lists.

Sangli (Jilha) Nagaer Vachnalya, Public Library of Sangli City:

Sangli Nager Vachnalya one of the oldest public library in Maharashtra. It was established in 1879 at Sangli and is known as Sri Dhundiraj Club. It was not just a library but a tradition of inculcating reading culture through many activities throughout the year. The library has received a valuable donation of cash and goods from the Rajaram Mohanrai Library Foundation, Calcutta. Programs like lectures, seminars, singing, and various competitions are organized in the Velenkar Hall of the Sangli Nager Vachnalya.

Sangli was hit by floods for the first time in 2005. The water reached the doors of the library but the collection was not damaged. Floods in August 2019 destroyed 66,000 books and some valuable manuscripts, computers and furniture. They were submerged for several days in eight feet deep water. Most of the books were on the ground floor to enable easy access. It became a pulp. As there was no space to dry all the books in the library, They took the help from locals. Many organizations, Shivaji University College Library Association, students from different colleges, locals were helped to retrieve the information. During this time, the library has received dryers, heaters, generators, tables, chairs, projectors, computers, printers and books as donations from the community. V.P. Institute of Management Studies and Research, Sangli had helped to retrieve the digital data of the library. Currently, the library has kept the books on the upper floor to avoid such damage again.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data:**Table No.1: Total Number of staff**

Faculties	Number
Librarian	1
Assistant Librarian	1
Clerk	1
Peon	2
Technical Staff	1

Observation:

Table No.1 shows that Sangli (Jilha) Nager Vachnalya have 1 permanent librarian, 1 Assistant librarian, 2 Peon, 1 Clerk and 1 Technical Staff.

From the observation it has been cleared that sufficient staff is available in the library.

Table No.2: Library has separate building.

Sr. No.	Opinion	
1	Yes	√
2	No	

Table No.2 shows that Sangli (Jilha) Nager Vachnalya has its own building.

Table No.3: Total Collection in the Library

Sr. No.	Collections	No.
1.	Books	70000
2.	News Papers	15
3.	Manuscript	450
4.	Magazines	30
5.	CD/DVD	00
6.	e-Books	00
7.	e-journals	00
8.	Encyclopedia	18
9.	Dictionaries	10
10.	Reports	00
11.	Handbooks	00

Table No.3 shows that library has 70000 Books, 15 News papers, 450 Manuscripts, 30 Magazines, 18 Encyclopedia and 10 Dictionaries but they don't have e-Books, e-journals, CD/DVD , Reports and Handbooks.

From the above table it has been noted that Sangli (Jilha) Nager Vachnalya don't have any electronic resources.

Table No.4: Library have hazardous elements that can cause a disaster

Sr. No.	Causes	Less possibility	Strong possibility	Definitely
1.	Water (burst pipes or heavy rains leading to flooding)		√	
2.	Poor storage and environmental conditions (dampness leading to mould growth)	√		
3.	Inadequate security (leading to theft)	√		
4.	Building deficiencies-poorly maintained buildings	√		
5.	Landslides	√		
6.	Combustible substance in the library or near the library	√		
7.	Poor drainage system		√	

Table No.4 shows that library has less possibility of disaster from Poor storage and environmental conditions, Inadequate security, Building

deficiencies-poorly maintained buildings, Landslides, Combustible substance in the library or near the library and strong

possibility of disasters form water and Poor drainage system.

From the above observation it has been found that there is a high possibility

Table No. 5: Availability of preventive measures in libraries

5.1 Water Disaster Preventive Measures

Sr. No.	Preventative measures	Yes	No	Don't know
1	White blotting paper		√	
2	Sponges		√	
3	Rubber boots and gloves		√	
4	Vacuum cleaner		√	
5	Plastic crates and boxes		√	
6	Polythene sheet, polythene bags		√	
7	Lightning Isolator	√		

Table No.5.1 shows that white blotting paper, sponge, rubber boots and gloves, vacuum cleaner, plastic crates and boxes, polythene sheets, polythene bags are water disaster prevention measures not available in the library and lightning isolator is available in the library.

From the above observation it has been found that only a lightning isolator is

5.3 Digital Disaster Preventive Measures

Sr. No.	Preventative measures	Yes	No	Don't know
1	Backup on the same computer	√		
2	Backup store outside the library		√	
3	Back up on external medium		√	
4	Back up on cloud		√	
5	Maintenance of Electrical Equipment's	√		
6	Automatic tripping of electrical system in case of fire or short circuit	√		
7	Anti-virus software and Up gradation	√		
8	Use of Password	√		
9	Uninterrupted power supply (UPS) in case power failure	√		
10	Generator in case power failure	√		
11	Maintenance of Electric Connections	√		
12	Proper electrical earthing	√		
13	New electrical system	√		

of disaster due to water and poor drainage system in Sangli Nager Vachnalya.

a water disaster prevention measure available.

5.2 Fire Disaster Preventive Measures

Sr. No.	Preventative measures	Yes	No	Don't know
1	Fire extinguisher	√		
2	Fire and Smoke alarms		√	
3	Sand buckets		√	
4	Water tank	√		
5	Water Sprinklers		√	
6	Pails for Fetching water	√		

Table No.5.2 shows that Fire extinguisher, water tank, pails for Fetching water are fire disaster prevention measures are available in the library and fire and smoke alarms, sand buckets, water sprinklers are not available in the library.

From the above observation it is seen that 50% fire disaster preventive measures are not available.

Table No.5.3 shows that backup on the same computer, maintenance of electrical equipment's, automatic tripping of electrical system in case of fire or short circuit, use of password, uninterrupted power supply (UPS) in case power failure, generator in case power failure, maintenance of electric connections, proper electrical earthing, New electrical system are digital disaster preventive measures available in the library and backup store outside the library, backup on external medium, backup on cloud are not available in the library.

From the above observation it is seen that backups are not kept outside the library.

5.4 Earthquake Disaster Preventive Measures

Sr. No.	Preventative measures	Yes	No	Don't know
1	Building is earthquake resistant		√	
2	Regular structural audit	√		

Table No.5.4 shows that library building is not earthquake resistant but structural audit is taken regularly.

From the above observation it is noted that partial facility regarding earthquake disaster preventive measure is available.

5.5 Biological Disaster Preventive Measures

Sr. No.	Preventative measures	Yes	No	Don't know
1	Regular spraying of insecticides	√		
2	Termite preventive measures	√		
3	Pest control	√		
4	Rodenticides	√		

Table No.5.5 shows that regular spraying of insecticides, termite preventive measures, pest control, Rodenticides Preventative measures are available in the library.

5.6 Safety precautions during covid-19 pandemic period

Sr. No.	Preventative measures	Yes	No	Don't know
1	Hand Sanitizer	√		
2	Air Purifier		√	
3	Transparent acrylic shields		√	
4	Masks	√		
5	Gloves	√		
6	Square Footage	√		
7	Drop box	√		
8	Infrared Thermometer		√	
9	A bin for used masks	√		

Table No.5.6 shows that hands sanitizer, masks, gloves, square footage, drop box and a bin for used masks are the safety preventative measures during covid-19 pandemic period were available in the library. Infrared thermometer, air purifier, transparent acrylic shields preventative measures were not available.

From the above observation it has been noted that most preventative measures were available in library during covid-19 pandemic period.

5.7 Other Preventive Measures

Sr. No.	Preventative measures	Yes	No	Don't know
1	Grills on Windows	√		
2	CCTVs	√		
3	Helmets and headlights		√	
4	First aid boxes		√	
5	RFID Gates and tags in Books		√	
6	Trolleys		√	
7	Aprons/protective cloths		√	
8	“Do's and Don'ts” displayed at appropriate locations		√	
9	Maps and escape route are displayed		√	
10	Emergency exit door	√		

Table No.5.7 shows that helmets and headlights, first aid boxes, first aid boxes, RFID Gates and tags in Books, trolleys, aprons/protective cloths, “Do's and Don'ts” displayed at appropriate locations, maps and escape route are the preventive measures not available in the library.

From the above discussion it has been recorded that most preventative measures were not available in library.

Table No. 6 library has insurance policy

Sr. No.	Parameters	Yes	No	Don't know
1	Furniture	√		
2	Books	√		
3	Special collections	√		
4	Fine art		√	
5	Shelving	√		
6	Computers	√		
7	Library records		√	
8	Motor vehicles (library van)			√
9	Building	√		

Table No.6 shows that library has insurance policy of furniture, books, special collections, shavings, computers and building. Library don't have insurance policy for fine art and library records.

From the above observation it has been noted that library has 70% insurance policy for its equipments.

Table No. 7 Availability of Disaster Management Plan:

Sr. No.	Status	Yes	No	Don't know
1	Library have disaster management plan	√		
2	Disaster management plan is updated regularly		√	

Table No.7 indicates that the library has a disaster management plan but the plan is not updated regularly.

Conclusion:

From the above observation and discussion, following conclusions were drawn

1. Sangli Nager Vachnalya the public library of Sangli city has its own building but the building is not earthquake resistant.
2. The library has high possibility of disaster due to water and poor drainage system.
3. In order to fight with water disaster, library should have availability of preventive measures like white blotting paper, sponge, rubber boots and gloves, vacuum cleaner, plastic crates and boxes, polythene sheets, polythene bags.
4. 80% of the digital disaster preventive measures were available in the library.
5. All the biological disaster preventive measures were available in the library.
6. 70% of the safety preventative measures were available in the

- library during covid-19 pandemic period.
7. 70% insurance policy has taken for library equipment.
 8. The library has window grills, CCTV and emergency exit doors for security measures.
 9. Sangli Nager Vachnalya has a disaster management plan.

Suggestions:

On the basis of the above conclusions, the following suggestions were made.

1. The risks and vulnerabilities of Sangli Nagar Vachnalya Library should be regularly assessed.
2. Sangli Nagar Library is a public library which has various important resources, to protect these resources from any disaster these resources need to be digitized and archived in digital form.
3. To prevent the loss of the data, the data must be regularly backed up. Backup must be stored in different devices like pen drive, hard disk also on Google Drive, Cloud Storage. Duplicate copy of data storage must be store outside of the library.
4. Fire and smoke alarm preventive measures should be essential for early warning of any kind of fire disaster.
5. Motor vehicle should be essential for transportation.
6. As there is a high possibility of water disaster in the library, it is necessary to have extensive provision of water disaster prevention measures.
7. Adequate disaster facilities and equipment should be acquired for quick response during a disaster in the Sangli Nagar Vachnalya .

8. Sangli Nager Vachnalya must have to updated their disaster management plan regularly.

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